

Operator	Description
Pattern Expression Mutation	
PFP ☆	Adds/Removes the parenthesis in a followed by operation
PGR ☆	Removes the guard expressions
PNR ☆	Removes the not the keyword of the negated conditional expressions in the pattern
POC ☆	Changes the order of the events in a followed by operation
POM ☆	Increases/Decreases the timer value by one unit in the pattern observer (timer:at , timer:interval)
PRE ☆	Replaces the query pattern by the pattern filter expression
Windows Mutation	
WLM ☆	Increases/Decreases the data window length by one
WTM ☆	Increases/Decreases the time window by one
WBL ☆	Turns a batch window length into an ordinary window length
WBT ☆	Turns a batch window time into an ordinary window time
Injection Attack Mutation	
IWR ☆	Removes the "where" condition from a query
ICN	negates the condition expression of a query
Replacement Mutation	
RAF	Replaces an aggregate function (max , min , avg , sum , count , median , stddev , avedev) by another of the same kind. The distinct keyword could also be added
RAO	Replaces an arithmetic operator (+, -, *, /, %) by another of the same kind
RBR	Replaces each between-condition a between x AND y by a > x AND a <= y , a >= x AND a < y and its negative
RGR	Removes a group-by expression, and adds an appropriate aggregation function
RJR	Replaces the keywords inner , left outer , right outer , full outer , outer of the "join" clause by another of the same kind
RLM	Exchanges a wildcard character (% , _) in the "like" expression patterns
RLA	Adds a wildcard character (% , _) at the beginning and at the end of the "like" expression patterns
RAW	Removes a wildcard character (% , _) at the beginning of the "like" expression patterns
RBW	Removes a wildcard character (% , _) at the end of the "like" expression patterns
RLO	Replaces a logical operator (and , or) by another of the same kind
RNO	Replaces a number e by e + 1 and e - 1
RNW	Exchanges the keyword is null and is not null
ROM	Exchanges or adds (if it does not exist) a keyword asc , desc in "order by" expressions
ROS	changes the order of the properties in the "order by" expressions
RRO	Replaces a relational operator (=, <>, <, >, <=, >=) by another of the same kind
RRR ₁ ☆	Exchanges a single row function {(cast , instanceof), (prevwindow , prevcount)}
RRR ₂ ☆	Exchanges a single row function (prev , prevtail , prior)
RSC	Replaces or adds (if it does not exist) a keyword in the select clause (rstream , irstream). The distinct keyword can be also added
RSR ₁	Replaces the keyword in type I subqueries (all , any , some) by another keyword of type I, type II or type III subqueries with the appropriate modifications
RSR ₂	Replaces the keyword in type II subqueries, (in , not in) by another of the keywords of type II, type I or type III subqueries with the appropriate modifications
RSR ₃	Exchanges, in type III subqueries, the keyword (exist , not exist)
RTU ☆	Replaces one time unit (milliseconds , seconds , minutes , hours , days) by another of the same kind

Table Esper EPL mutation operator definitions